

Chelate Stability Constants and Chelate Hydrolysis Constants of Vanadium (IV) with Multidentate Ligands

SUREKHA G. TAK, O. P. SUNAR & C. P. TRIVEDI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur.

Received 25 February 1971

Chelate stability constants of aspartic acid (ASPA), N, N'-ethylenediaminedisuccinic acid (EDDS) and N, N'-ethylenediamine-bis (α -glutaric acid) (EDG) with vanadium (IV) ions have been investigated. It is found that hydroxocomplexes are formed at higher pH. Chelate formation constants, chelate hydrolysis constants and chelate olation constants are reported in the ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO_3) at 25°. Hydrolysis constants are reported for the 1:1 vanadium (IV) chelates of EDDS and EDG. Log K_1 were calculated as 8.39, 12.89 and 12.49 for ASPA, EDDS and EDG respectively. The metal-ligand ratio was found to be 1:2 in aspartic acid-metal system only and log K_2 was calculated as 6.04.

Previous investigations have reported many polydentate ligands and their proton-ligand as well as metal-ligand stability constants¹⁻⁴. Recently Trivedi *et al.* reported the synthesis and chelating tendencies of N,N'-ethylenediaminedisuccinic acid (EDDS)⁵ and N,N'-ethylenediamine-bis(α -glutaric acid) (EDG)⁶ with bivalent metal ions. The present investigation deals with the study of composition and chelating tendencies of the three ligands ASPA, EDDS and EDG with vanadium (IV) ion. The chelate formation constants, chelate hydrolysis constants and chelate olation constants have been evaluated for the 1 : 1 vanadium (IV) chelates of EDDS and EDG.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of EDDS and EDG has been described in earlier communications^{5,6}. Aspartic acid was a gift sample from Hexagon Laboratories, U.S.A. Solutions of metal salts, sodium hydroxide, potassium nitrate etc., were prepared by weighing AnalaR or B.D.H. grade reagents. Vanadyl sulphate ($\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) was used for preparing the metal solution. Standardization of the metal solution was done by titrating it with sodium hydroxide in the presence of excess disodium salt of EDTA according to the method of Schwarzenbach⁷.

The experimental method consisted of potentiometric titrations of the ligand in the absence of and in the presence of the metal ions being investigated with standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.0M) solution. The temperature of the systems was regulated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the ionic strength was maintained constant by using a medium of 0.1M potassium nitrate. Carbondioxide free nitrogen was passed slowly through the experimental solution. The pH was measured by a Cambridge (Bench type) pH-meter using glass and calomel electrodes. The measurements were checked before and after the titration with standard buffers.

Calculations : Proton-ligand stability constants of EDDS and EDG and metal-chelate stability constants were calculated by Bjerrum's⁸ and Irving and Rossotti⁹ methods and are shown in Table 1.

The computational methods described by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ were employed to determine the successive protonation constants for the ligands and successive formation constants for VO(IV) complexes. The *pK* values of EDDS are 3.25, 4.0, 8.5 and 9.4 and that of EDG are 3.75, 4.85, 8.93 and 9.75.

Mathematical Treatment of Data : In the VO(IV) chelate systems studied with equimolar concentrations of EDDS and EDG, four species have been shown to exist; a normal chelate VOA^{2-} ; a monohydroxo compound VO(OH)A^{3-} ; a dihydroxo species $\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}^{4-}$; and a dimer $[\text{VO(OH)A}]_2^{6-}$. The solution equilibria may be defined by the equations :

If T_{OH} represents the hydroxide added to a solution of the normal chelate, $[\text{VOA}]$, during the titration, then

$$T_{\text{OH}} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-] = [\text{VO(OH)A}] + 2[\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}] + 2[(\text{VO(OH)A})_2] \quad \dots (5)$$

In equation 5, charges of ions have been eliminated for achieving clarity, Since the concentration of the dihydroxo chelate is small in the region preceding the crossover point.

$$T_{\text{OH}} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-] = [\text{VO(OH)A}] + 2[(\text{VO(OH)A})_2] \quad \dots (6)$$

The total concentration of chelate species, T_{A} , is defined by the relationship

$$T_{\text{A}} = [\text{VOA}] + [\text{VO(OH)A}] + [\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}] + 2[(\text{VO(OH)A})_2] \quad \dots (7)$$

Therefore in the region preceding the crossover

$$T_{\text{A}} = [\text{VOA}] + [\text{VO(OH)A}] + 2[(\text{VO(OH)A})_2] \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$\text{VOA} = T_A - T_{OH} - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-] \quad \dots (9)$$

Combination of equations 2, 4 and 6 gives the expression

$$\frac{T_{OH} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{VOA}]/[\text{H}^+]} = K_{\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}} + 2K_{(\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A})_2} \frac{[\text{VOA}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (10)$$

Thus if a dimer is formed; a straight line is obtained when $(T_{OH} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-])[\text{H}^+] / [\text{VOA}]$ is plotted against $[\text{VOA}]/[\text{H}^+]$, the slope of which is equal to $2K_{(\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A})_2}$ and the intercept at $[\text{VOA}]/[\text{H}^+] = 0$ is equal to $K_{\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}}$.

$K_{\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}}$ may be calculated from the value of $-\log \text{H}^+$ where the curves cross, in accordance with the relationship

$$pK_{\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}} = 2(-\log[\text{H}^+]) \quad \dots (11)$$

Since at this point it may be assumed that the concentration of $\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}$ and of VOA are equal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dissociation steps of ASPA, EDDS and EDG are quite similar except that the former involves the dissociation of two protons, rather than four.

The chemical properties of the vanadyl ion often have been compared with those of Cu(II) . Thus the colour and coordination requirements of VO(IV) and Cu(II) seem to be quite similar. The hydrolytic tendencies of these two ions also seem to be similar although a large part is being played by the presence of the OXO group on VO(IV) . In general the data obtained in this research indicate that the vanadyl ion does form 1 : 1 stable complex at low $p\text{H}$ but at higher $p\text{H} > 8$, the mono-hydroxo, dihydroxo and perhaps a dimer species are formed.

1 : 1 VO(IV) —EDDS and EDG Systems : The fall in $p\text{H}$ by adding metal ion in ligand solutions explains the formation of the complexes. The constant horizontal distance between the two sets of curves (Fig. 1, curves B, B' and C, C') indicates that the complexes formed in the initial state are very stable, possess constant composition and are of the same nature.

One inflection at $a \approx 4$ as well as colour change correspond to the following reactions :

Beyond $p\text{H}$ 8.5 second buffer region starts. The colour of the reaction mixture gradually changes to yellow from violet. An inflection at $m \approx 5.5$ where the conversion of VOA to VO(OH)A and $\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}$ has taken place, is observed. Finally at $m \approx 6$, $\text{VO(OH)}_2\text{A}$ species predominates. The titration curves for different concentrations of the VO(IV) —EDG chelate show that an increase in metal chelate concentration results in a shift of the buffer

regions to lower pH values in the m interval from 1 to 4, where m represents the number of moles of sodium hydroxide added per mole of metal ion. Beyond the crossover point of the curves at $m = 4$ the second buffer region is displaced to higher pH values with a corresponding increase in the concentration of the metal chelate. The greater requirement of the base at a particular pH as a result of the higher concentration of metal chelate is an indication of the formation of a polymer of the type $[VO(OH)A]_2$.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of 1 : 1 VO(IV) chelates of ASPA, EDDS and EDG. α and m are the moles of base added per mole of ligand and metal ion respectively.

Curve A, B and C— $5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ each ASPA, EDDS and EDG.

Curve A', B' and C'—1 : 1 VO(IV) and ligand ($5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ each).

A plot $(T_{OH} + [H^+] - [OH^-])[H^+]/[VOA]$ vs. $[VOA]/[H^+]$ gives a straight line for 1 : 1 VO(IV)—EDG system, which verifies the formation of the dimer chelate compound. Similar plots were obtained for the VO(IV)—EDDS chelates. A summary of the equilibrium constants obtained is given in Table 1.

1 : 2 VO(IV)—EDDS and EDG Systems : The 1 : 2 VO(IV)—EDDS and EDG systems were studied. There is long buffer region from $\alpha = 0$ to $\alpha = 3$, where only reaction is the neutralization of the H^+ ion which was displaced at the start of titration by complete formation of the 1 : 1 VO(IV) chelate and from the extra molecule of the ligand. An inflection at $\alpha = 3$ shows that the 1 : 1 complex is formed. The second buffer region starts beyond

TABLE 1

Equilibrium Constants for VO(IV) Chelates $t = 25 \pm .1^\circ$ $\mu = 0.10$ (KNO₃)

Ligand	Method	$\log K_{VOA}$	$\log K_{VOA_2}$	$\log \beta_2$	$pK_{VO(OH)A}$	$pK_{VO(OH)_2A}$	$pK(VO(OH)A)_2$
ASPA :	a	8.40	6.05	14.45	—	—	—
	b	8.39	6.05	14.45	—	—	—
	c	8.38	6.03	14.41	—	—	—
	Mean	8.39	6.04	14.44	—	—	—
EDDS :	a	13.10	—	—	9.60	18.00	15.08
	c	12.69	—	—	—	—	—
	Mean	12.89	—	—	—	—	—
EDG :	a	12.40	—	—	8.31	16.90	14.71
	c	12.58	—	—	—	—	—
	Mean	12.49	—	—	—	—	—

a—Extension of Bjerrum's method.

b—Method of successive approximations.

c—Direct calculation Method.

$pH \approx 8$ at which the colour of the reaction mixture has been also changed. Beyond a value of $a = 3$ ($pH \approx 8$) the chelate begins to hydrolyse. Since there is no precipitate even at high pH values, a soluble hydroxo complex is formed. The drifting of pH values is noted at high pH above $a = 5$. This phenomenon is an indication of even furtherolation of the VO(OH)A chelate. It should be noted since no precipitation is observed in any of the systems, that the hydrolysis therefore produces only soluble, though perhaps very complex, polynuclear chelates containing hydroxo bridges¹¹.

1 : 1 and 1 : 2 VI(IV)—ASPA Systems : Curves A and A' (Fig. 1) represent pH titrations of the pure ligand and ligand-metal mixture respectively. The inflex in curve A' (Fig. not given) at $a = 2$ corresponds to release of all the protons in the system. The following equations may explain the chemical equilibria :

The formation curve (not given) also indicates the predominance of 1 : 2 complex at higher pH . The K_{VOA} and K_{VOA_2} values are given in Table 1.

The authors are grateful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Jodhpur for providing research facilities and to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of us (O.P.S.).

R E F E R E N C E S

1. S. Westerback, K. S. Rajan and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 2567.
2. A. Yingst and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6927.
3. T. A. Bohigian Jr. and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 832.
4. S. Chaberek Jr. and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 6228.
5. O. P. Sunar, Ph.D. Thesis, Jodhpur University (1971).
6. C. P. Trivedi, O. P. Sunar and Surekha Tak, Paper accepted for publication in *J. inorg. nuclear Chem.*
7. G. Schwarzenbach and W. Beidermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1948, **31**, 331.
8. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son., Copenhagen, 1957.
9. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
11. A. E. Martell, S. Chaberek Jr, R. C. Courtney and S. Westerback and Hyytainen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 3036.